

Knowledge, Attitude & Hesitancy Towards the Covid-19 Booster Vaccination Among the General Public in North India

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Abstract

Background: The Covid-19 adversely impacted human life, challenged public health, and led to economic disruption worldwide. Vaccines were introduced to reduce the threats linked to Covid-19 infection, related hospitalization and/or death; but as time has elapsed since vaccination initially began, the efficacy of vaccine has gone down. Moreover, people who have a weakened immune system might be poorly protected against the different variants of Covid-19. This survey conducted amidst the general public of North India strives to evaluate the Knowledge, Attitude and Hesitancy towards the Covid-19 booster vaccination.

Materials and Methods: The survey was administered using an online questionnaire and 206 participants responded to it. This descriptive cross-sectional study focused on North India's general public. Convenience non-probability sampling collected data from March 24 to May 18, 2022, via a Google Form shared through Facebook and WhatsApp. Participants aged 16 and above, were requested to complete the questionnaire without incentives. The survey comprised 7 sections: Objectives and consent, Demographics, Medical history, Vaccination status, Knowledge, COVID-19 vaccine acceptance (Likert scale), and Perception questions. Ethical approval was obtained. Statistical analysis, performed with IBM SPSS, involved bar graphs, frequency tables, pie charts, and Chi-square tests for variable connections at significance levels of $p \leq 0.01$ and $p \leq 0.05$.

Results: Out of all the respondents, 56% were female and 44% were male; 55.8% of respondents belonged to the age group 21-30years. The Covid-19 booster vaccine was already taken by 40 participants (19.4%) and 80.1% agreed to advocate other people to get the booster shot of the vaccine. 65% of the participants reported about the occurrences of unpleasant events post primary vaccination. 73.3% had heard about the booster dose of the Covid-19 vaccine. The results described that 43 (20.9%) respondents were completely reluctant to take the booster shot of the Covid-19 vaccine.

Conclusion: A satisfactory approach to increase awareness and acceptance of vaccines is needed. Using an advanced educational framework, the general population needs to be educated about the risks associated with avoiding or delaying vaccination. Highlighting the social benefits of getting vaccinated could prove to be beneficial to improve attitude towards vaccines.

Keywords: Vaccine hesitancy; booster dose; vaccination; willingness; India.

1. Introduction

The World Health Organization (WHO) designated Covid-19 a global pandemic on March 11, 2020, tracing its origins to Wuhan, China in December 2019. This viral outbreak, caused by the Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome-Coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), triggered a devastating global health crisis.^[1] Notably, Covid-19 not only jeopardized millions of lives but also triggered widespread economic downturns due to prolonged lockdowns.

Research identified that Covid-19 primarily spreads through close human contact within 6 feet (2 meters), mainly through respiratory droplets expelled via coughing and sneezing. Its symptoms vary widely, encompassing cough, fever, fatigue, and, in a minority of cases, gastrointestinal issues. The virus often inflicts severe damage on the respiratory system, yet it can also harm multiple other organs by binding to receptors in the lungs, brain, heart, kidneys, and more.^[2]

Amid advancements in clinical research and vaccine development, humanity gained a better grasp of the SARS-CoV-2 virus. Nevertheless, the emergence of variants such as Alpha, Beta, Gamma, Delta, and Omicron perpetuated global suffering.^[3] As of May 9, 2022, WHO reports documented over 515 million confirmed Covid-19 cases, with a staggering death toll of 6.25 million. Encouragingly, vaccination campaigns managed to administer 11.5 billion vaccine doses.^[4]

Vaccination emerged as the most effective strategy against infectious diseases. The U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) authorized the emergency use of Covid-19 vaccines for individuals aged 16 and older on December 11, 2020.^[5] However, vaccine acceptance depended greatly on public knowledge, attitudes, and perceptions.^[6] Vaccine hesitancy remained a challenge, endangering the success of vaccination efforts.^[7,8] Overcoming this hurdle required both widespread education and addressing misinformation.

Booster shots became imperative due to the gradual waning of vaccine effectiveness over time. Notably, the U.S. approved three vaccines—Pfizer-BioNTech, Moderna, and Johnson & Johnson^[9]—while India authorized Covishield, Covaxin, Sputnik V, ZyCoV-D, Corbevax, and Covovax.^[10]

In Northern India, a survey aimed to assess public knowledge, attitudes, and hesitancy towards Covid-19 booster shots. This initiative sought to understand reasons behind vaccine hesitancy and acceptance, contributing to effective pandemic management and fostering a positive vaccination environment. It emphasized cultural relevance and underlined the importance of government and public health efforts in promoting vaccine adoption and cultivating a favorable vaccine perception within society.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study Design, Participants and Data Collection

It was a descriptive cross-sectional study performed on the general public in North India. The convenience non-probability sampling technique was utilised and data was gathered from the 24th of March 2022 to 18th of May 2022. The survey was based on a proprietary Google Form in English language which was then shared by all project members using its access link via online social networking sites like- Facebook and WhatsApp. The participants of the survey were requested to complete the questionnaire without a time limit. The participants did not get any kind of incentives for completing the survey. In the beginning of the Google form for this survey, the participants were enlightened regarding the nature of the study, and the Inclusion criteria comprised of: (1) 16 years of age and older (2) willingness to take part in the study (3) resident of North India; and Exclusion criteria: (1) age less than 16 years (2) medical professional (3) incomplete forms. The questionnaire consisted of 7 sections: Section 1 provided information on the Objective of the study and took consent of the participant, then the participant was redirected

to the second section; Section 2 consisted of questions on Demographic information such as Gender, Age, Area of residence, Marital status, Education, Family, Occupation and Health Insurance Coverage; Section 3 and section 4 focused on medical history and vaccination status respectively. For section 5 (Knowledge), respondents had to choose from these three choices: Yes, No, and Do not know. Section 6 comprised of questionnaire on the “Acceptance of COVID- 19 vaccine” with answers based on Likert scale- Strongly agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, and Strongly disagree; and Section 7 had perception-based questions with yes/no and Multiple checkboxes as options.

2.2. Ethical Considerations

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and approved by the Ethics Committee of Sri Sukhmani Dental College & Hospital, Derabassi, Punjab, India (SSDC/ERC/12/2022/28) and was conducted in agreement with the ethical standards of the declaration of Helsinki.

2.3 Statistical Analysis

The IBM SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) statistical version 20 was used for statistical analysis. This analysis includes- bar, frequency table, pie chart, and link of variables deduced using the Chi-square test. Two-tailed levels of significance were used for all statistical tests- $p \leq 0.01$ and $p \leq 0.05$.

3. Results

3.1 Demographic data

206 participants gave consent and responded to this online survey. Women (56.1%) and people living as nuclear families (71.7%) in urban areas (90.7%) constituted the majority of the respondents. The details of the age of the participants were as follows: 16 (7.8%) aged <20, 115(55.8%) aged 21-30, 17 (18.3%) aged 31-40, 19 (9.2%) aged 41-50, 30 (14.6%) aged 51-60 and 9 (4.4%) aged >61. 60% of the participants were employed.

Variable Name	Categories	n (%)
Gender	Male	91(44.2%)
	Female	115(55.8%)
Age	<=20	16(7.8%)
	21-30	115(55.8%)
	31-40	17(8.3%)

	41-50	19(9.2%)
	51-60	30(14.6%)
	>60	9(4.4%)
Area of Residence	Urban	186(90.3%)
	Rural	20(9.7%)
Marital Status	Married	81(39.3%)
	Unmarried	118(57.3%)
	Other	7(3.4%)
Education	Primary School	1(5%)
	Secondary School	12(5.8%)
	Undergraduate	2(1.0%)
	Graduate	84(40.8%)
	Post graduate	86(41.7%)
	Doctorate/MPhil	14(6.8%)
	Diploma	7(3.4%)
Family	Nuclear	147(71.4%)
	Joint	59(28.6%)
Occupation	Employed	124(60.2%)
	Housewife	14(6.8%)
	Unemployed	68(33.0%)
Health Insurance coverage	Yes	114(55.3%)
	No	68(33.0%)
	Don't Know	24(11.7%)

[Table 1] Demographic characteristics of the participants (n=206)

3.2 Medical history and vaccination status

19.9% of the total Participants had chronic diseases; relatives of 64.6% of the participants got Covid-19 infection; 36.1% of the respondents had an infection with Covid-19; 97.1% had been vaccinated with the first two shots of the COVID-19 vaccine, and about 1% needed hospital admission due to unfavourable reaction to the Covid-19 vaccine. 64.9% had experienced side effects like tiredness, fever, headache, chills, muscle ache, diarrhoea, and redness or pain around the injection site because of the Covid-19 vaccine. Only 19% had chronic diseases.

Questions	Yes	No	Don't know
Now that the third dose (booster dose) of the Covid-19 vaccine is available, have you heard about its availability at the health Centre?	73.2%	13.2%	13.7%
The mechanism by which the booster dose acts on the body is the same as the first two doses	37.1%	7.8%	55.1%
Does a previously infected person (with Covid-19) need a booster dose?	60%	4.9%	35.1%
Does the booster dose provide immunity against the different variants of Covid-19?	47.8%	6.8%	45.4%
Have you heard about anyone who had side effects with the booster dose of the vaccine even though there were no adverse effects with the first two doses?	11.2%	56.6%	32.2%
Does being vaccinated with the booster dose stop you from infecting other people with Covid-19?	22.4%	38%	39.5%
Is the booster dose given via an injection?	73.7%	0%	26.3%
Are you still required to take preventive measures (mask, social distancing) after the booster dose	79.5%	5.4%	15.1%

[Table 2] shows medical history and vaccination status of participants (n=206)

3.3 Participant's knowledge about the booster dose of COVID-19 vaccine

Questions	Yes	No	Don't know
Now that the third dose (booster dose) of the vaccine is available, have you heard about its availability at the health Centre?	73.2%	13.2%	13.7%
The mechanism by which the booster dose acts on the body is the same as the first two doses	37.1%	7.8%	55.1%

Does a previously infected person (with Covid-19) need a booster dose?	60%	4.9%	35.1%
Does the booster dose provide immunity against the different variants of Covid-19?	47.8%	6.8%	45.4%
Have you heard about anyone who had side effects with the booster dose of the vaccine even though there were no adverse effects with the first two doses?	11.2%	56.6%	32.2%
Does being vaccinated with the booster dose stop you from infecting other people with Covid-19?	22.4%	38%	39.5%
Is the booster dose given via an injection?	73.7%	0%	26.3%
Are you still required to take preventive measures (mask, social distancing) after the booster dose	79.5%	5.4%	15.1%

[Table3] Outcome of analysed factors that impact the knowledge about the Booster dose of COVID-19 Vaccine.

3.4 Participant's Attitude about COVID-19 vaccine booster dose

This section consisted of 6 statements with their responses based on a 5-point Likert scale (5 = strongly agree, 4 = agree, 3 = neutral, 2 = disagree, 1 = strongly disagree). Most participants (53.9%) had no concerns with respect to the vaccine. 32% of the participants were concerned about side effects of the vaccine. The participants mainly trusted the doctors (63.6%) and then the government agencies (56.3%) for information pertaining to vaccines. About 6.8% did not trust any source.

Questions	Answers	Percentage
Everyone should take the booster dose for Covid-19 vaccine:	Strongly disagree	1.5%
	Disagree	2.4%
	Neutral	17.0%
	Agree	25.2%
	Strongly agree	53.9%

Booster dose may show side effects on the body:	Strongly disagree	2.4%
	Disagree	13.6%
	Neutral	51.9%
	Agree	26.2%
	Strongly agree	5.8%
Booster dose of the vaccine is safe and effective to use:	Strongly disagree	1.5%
	Disagree	1.0%
	Neutral	33.0%
	Agree	43.2%
	Strongly agree	21.4%
Booster dose should be given every 6 monthly:	Strongly disagree	4.4%
	Disagree	16.0%
	Neutral	49.5%
	Agree	23.8%
	Strongly agree	6.3%
Booster dose should be provided free for everyone by the government:	Strongly disagree	5%
	Disagree	3.4%
	Neutral	17.5%
	Agree	29.6%
	Strongly agree	49.0%
I am ready to pay for the booster if needed:	Strongly disagree	2.9%
	Disagree	8.3%

	Neutral	25.7%
	Agree	41.7%
	Strongly agree	21.4%
Who do you trust the most for any details related to the booster dose of the vaccine?	Government agencies	56.3%
	Doctors & healthcare professionals	63.6%
	Literature by pharmaceutical brands	13.1%
	Scientific literature	22.3%
	Friends and family	10.7%
	Internet & social media (Facebook, Twitter etc.)	5.8%
	Health care providers: Physicians, nurses, etc.	5%
	I do not trust any source	6.8%

[Table 4] Results of all the questions associated with the attitude towards the booster dose of COVID-19 vaccine.

3.5 Participant's Hesitancy about COVID-19 vaccine booster dose

Over 80% of participants were willing to use the vaccine and advocate others to get booster doses at the earliest owing to certain factors as shown in Graph 1a. However, the reason that the remaining 20% of them were unwilling to get vaccinated was based on the unpredictability associated with the vaccine's safety as shown in Graph 1b.

Graph 1 below showcases the various reasons linked to the readiness to the COVID-19 vaccine and their distribution.

Graph 1a: Motivation for getting the booster dose of COVID-19 Vaccine

Graph 1b below elaborates the cause for reluctance for booster dose. Participants who were reluctant mainly justified by saying that they would develop natural immunity (10.2%), or were concerned with changes in the normal functioning of their immune system (6.3%). About 6% of respondents did not have faith in vaccines and 6% believed that they do not need the booster dose as they have already taken the Covid-19 vaccine dose at least once. According to 4.4% individuals, covid-19 is not a deadly disease and it can directly affect the body's natural

immunity.

Graph 1b: Reluctancy towards the booster dose of COVID-19 Vaccine

4. Discussion

In March-April 2022, a survey involving 206 volunteers from North India was conducted following the approval of the COVID-19 vaccine booster shot by the Ministry of Health, Government of India, on January 10, 2022.^[11] The survey aimed to evaluate Knowledge, Attitude, and Hesitancy toward the Covid-19 booster dose. Given the proven safety and efficacy of COVID-19 vaccines in combating the pandemic, governments globally endeavored to convey this message to their populations. To effectively combat the pandemic, halting virus transmission through herd immunity is vital, requiring a vaccination rate of at least 82%. Achieving this necessitates strong vaccine willingness and reduced hesitancy.^[12] With emerging Covid-19 variants and declining immunity after initial doses, receiving a booster shot became crucial for enhancing waning immunity.^[13]

Involving a predominantly urban population (90.3%), our survey revealed a 20% hesitancy rate toward the COVID-19 vaccine booster shot, an improvement over prior Indian studies.^[14] The booster shot's acceptance was influenced by individual case demographics and health status. Notably, individuals previously vaccinated with BCG and DPT vaccines were more hesitant, contrasting earlier research from China^[15] and Hong

Kong^[16] which linked prior flu vaccination with higher COVID-19 vaccine acceptance.^[16,17,18,19]

Females (56% of respondents) experienced more side effects (77.4%) compared to males (59.3%). The average knowledge score was 58.74%, indicating moderate awareness but room for improvement. Greater knowledge correlated with reduced vaccination hesitancy, reflecting the impact of health-seeking behavior on understanding disease susceptibility.^[20]

Trust, notably government trust (56.3%), played a vital role in vaccine acceptance.^[21] Rural areas (40%) showed less advocacy for booster shots compared to urban regions (17.7%). Chronic disease presence didn't significantly affect booster dose reluctance; in fact, those with chronic diseases were slightly more likely (0.5%) to take the booster, contradicting earlier findings.^[22] Given the higher vulnerability of COVID-19 patients with chronic conditions, timely vaccination remains crucial.^[23]

Efforts must be made to improve awareness regarding the ill-effects of COVID-19, and it must be emphasised on how the vaccine can help lessen the worsening of symptoms and prevent death associated with COVID-19 infection. People above and below the education levels of post-graduates were more likely to advocate others for booster dose. It was found that respondents with a higher educational degree were extra willing to get vaccinated with the COVID-19 booster vaccination in general. This was in-line with previously done similar researches^[24,25,26,27,28,29], for example, a study done on individuals with at least a postgraduate degree and who worked in the public sector in Saudi Arabia showed more inclination to get the COVID-19 vaccine.^[30] But it was in contrast to a survey that highlighted that people with lower education were keener to get vaccinated in comparison to people with higher education.^[25,31]

Government agencies were highly trusted for vaccine administration (56.3%). Similar strategies should be endorsed by the Ministry of Health to boost vaccination coverage. Elevating Covid-19 vaccine utilization, several steps can be taken: offering cost-free vaccines to all, ensuring equal distribution among target groups, particularly high-risk ones, and fostering vaccination through nationwide media campaigns. Enhancing community vaccine acceptance includes garnering support from community leaders and the government, maintaining a waiting list for interested residents not in the initial target group, and integrating behavioural science to effectively engage diverse groups. Professional coaching and risk communication training by experts require investment and time. The main motivation for the booster dose understood Covid-19's lethality (59.7%) and its link to vaccination's role in curbing cases. Trust in doctors played a role for 17.5%. Those with Covid-19-affected family or friends were less hesitant (19.5%) than those without (21.4%), aligning with other surveys.^[32] Respondents' main concerns included side effects, lack of knowledge, vaccine safety, and efficacy, contributing to reluctance for the Covid-19 booster dose. Similar

factors emerged in prior studies.^[33,34,35,36,37]

4.1 Strengths and Limitations

This survey for the population of Northern India took into account many variables which aptly apply to the demographics of a wide range of people in this part of the country. It was conducted shortly after the booster dose was approved by the GOI and hence paints a true picture of the opinions of the population without much gap between the date of approval for the booster dose and the survey. But this doesn't come without its limitations. One limitation of this survey was the use of convenience sampling via social media platforms like WhatsApp, Facebook. The dissemination of the respondents might not show the actual population since most respondents were internet users' young adults; older individuals or those with a lower socio-economic status may have been eliminated due to absence of Internet access. Secondly, the online self-reporting method may have introduced bias due to social acceptability and memory; hence the results may differ on a broader aspect. Thirdly, some important concerns may have gone unrecorded because we used a closed-ended questionnaire.

5. Conclusion

The survey is satisfactorily valid. It may help governments across the globe to acquire more components concerning the present and future endeavours to limit the spread of COVID-19. Additionally, assessments specific to a country should be done to evaluate public perceptions. Continuous education and awareness must be spread to enhance understanding, and to remove the possibility of any misconceptions or disinformation pertaining to the vaccine. Preferably, the information for public health education must be layman friendly. Community concerns, issues causing distrust and sensitivity to religious or philosophical beliefs should be directly addressed via strategies of promoting vaccine literacy and acceptance. Important information should reach all the residents of a nation, the ones residing in rural areas, and those who are not technology users. Various educational tools based on the internet, in-person interaction with the experts of the field, and printed material may benefit specific groups in the population, including religious groups.

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